

A Study of Effect of Yogic Practices on Dynamic Balance and Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players

Mrs. Asha Narendra Kunder¹ & Dr. Vasant G. Zende²

¹Research Student & Physical Education and Yoga Teacher, Queen Mary School, Mumbai

²Research Guide and Head, Dept. of Physical Education and Sports, Pratishthan Mahavidyalaya, Paithan, Affiliated to Dr.B.A.M. University, Chhatrapati Sambhaji Nagar, Maharashtra

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Abstract:

The purpose of the present study is to find out the effect of yogic practices on Dynamic Balance and Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho players. To achieve the purpose of the study 6 months yogic training program was conducted on 60 state level Kho Kho players. They were divided into two groups: Experimental and control groups. The experimental group underwent a specific yogic exercise training program. For the Pre Test and Post Test, the Dynamic Balance and Pulse Rate was measured with the help of Pulse rate was measured with the help of Y Balance Test and pulse oximeter apparatus respectively. Using the One way ANCOVA for statistical analysis, the study examined changes in these variables like Dynamic Balance and Pulse Rate over the course of 6 months intervention. The results demonstrated significant improvement in Dynamic Balance and Pulse Rate indicating that sustained engagement in yogic practices can lead to substantial motor fitness and physiological benefits for the Kho Kho players. These findings underscore the potential of yoga as a holistic approach to enhance athletic performance.

Keywords: Kho Kho, Yoga, Dynamic Balance, Pulse Rate, Y Balance Test.

Introduction:

Kho-Kho is one of the most popular indigenous games of India, requiring excellent motor fitness components such as speed, agility, flexibility, balance, and coordination along with optimal physiological efficiency. Due to the nature of the game, players are exposed to high physical and mental stress during training and competition. Modern training methods focus mainly on physical conditioning; however, yogic practices offer a holistic approach by improving both physical fitness and physiological functioning.

Yoga has been scientifically proven to enhance flexibility, muscular endurance, respiratory efficiency, and mental concentration. Therefore, it is essential to scientifically investigate the effect of yogic practices on

selected motor fitness and physiological variables of state level Kho-Kho players.

Hence the researcher studied the effect of yogic practises on motor fitness as well as Physiological Variables of State Level Kho-Kho players by conducting a study titled;

“A Study of Effect of Yogic Practices on Selected Motor fitness and Physiological Variables of State Level Kho Kho Players.”

Objectives:

The present study aims at collecting the scientific evidence about the effects of selected yogic practices on reaction time and blood pressure of state level Kho Kho players. Hence the objective of the study was

1. To compare the scores of Right leg Dynamic balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group .
2. To compare the scores of Left leg Dynamic balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group .
3. To compare the scores of Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group .

Hypothesis:

Depending upon the reviews of literature, research findings and researcher's understanding of the problem, it is hypothesised that-

H01 : There is no significant difference between the scores of Right leg Dynamic balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group.

H02 : There is no significant difference between the scores of Left leg Dynamic balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group.

H03: There is no significant difference between the scores of Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group.

Method of the Study:

The researcher has chosen a parallel group design and experimental method for conducting this study. This study consists of one control group and one experimental group of 30 players each. Only the experimental group received the specific Yoga training for the period of six months.

Pre Test and Post-test programs were organized before and after the experimental period of six months.

The Subjects / Sampling:

A total number of 60 State level male Kho Kho players of age group 15 to 19 years from Mumbai were selected for this study. The 60 State level players were pooled as a sample from the population of hundreds of state level players by using a purposive sampling method.

Selection of Variables and Tests:

After going through the related literature, the following dependent and independent variables are selected to collect the data at the pre-test and post-test and to render the training in between.

1) Dependent Variables:

- Dynamic Balance
- Pulse Rate

2) Independent Variables:

A set of 15 yogic practices including Omkar, standing postures, sitting postures, lying down postures, pranayam are chosen by the researcher for this study as independent variables on the basis of the fact that they are beneficial as they promote physical fitness required for sports.

Criterion Measures:

- Dynamic Balance is measured with the help of the Y Balance test.
- Pulse Rate is measured with the help of a Pulse Oximeter apparatus.

Statistical Procedure:

The pre and post tests data of all the selected subjects is analyzed by using descriptive statistics with the help of SPSS using One way ANCOVA .

Statistical Interpretation of Data Groupwise comparison of adjusted mean scores of Right Leg Dynamic Balance:

While comparing the adjusted mean scores of Right Leg Dynamic Balance of State

Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group by considering their Pre-Right Leg Dynamic Balance as covariate, Set of Yogic Practices was One Independent Variable, Pre-Right Leg Dynamic Balance was one Covariate

and Post-Right Leg Dynamic Balance was the Dependent Variable. Thus, the data were analysed with the help of One Way ANCOVA and the results are given in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Summary of One Way ANCOVA of Right Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players by taking their Pre-Right Leg Dynamic Balance as Covariate

Source of Variance	df	SSy.x	MSSy.x	Fy.x	Remark
Yogic Practices	1	119.455	119.455	35.606	p<0.01
Error	57	191.228	3.355		
Total	59				

From Table 1.1, it can be seen that the adjusted F-Value is 35.606 which is significant at 0.01 level with $df = 1/57$. It indicates that the adjusted mean scores of Right Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group differ significantly when their Pre-Right Leg Dynamic Balance was taken as Covariate.

Further, the adjusted mean score of Right Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group is 95.53 which is significantly higher than those of Control Group whose adjusted mean score of Right Leg Dynamic Balance is 92.71. It may, therefore, be said that Right Leg Dynamic Balance of students treated through Yogic Practices Group was found to be significantly superior to Control Group when groups were matched in respect of their Pre-Right Leg Dynamic Balance. The result also has been graphically presented in Figure 1.1

Figure 1.1: Group wise comparison of Adjusted Mean Scores of Right Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players.

Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between adjusted mean scores of Right Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group by considering their Pre-Right Leg Dynamic Balance as covariate is rejected.

Groupwise comparison of adjusted mean scores of Left Leg Dynamic Balance:

The Objective was to compare adjusted mean scores of Left Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group by considering their Pre-Left Leg Dynamic Balance as covariate. Here Strategy of Yogic Practices was One Independent Variable having two levels, namely, Asanas and Pranayama. Pre-Left Leg Dynamic Balance was

one Covariate and Post-Left Leg Dynamic Balance was the Dependent Variable. Thus, the

data were analysed with the help of One Way ANCOVA and the results are given in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2: Summary of One Way ANCOVA of Left Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players by taking their Pre-Left Leg Dynamic Balance as Covariate

Source of Variance	df	SSy.x	MSSy.x	Fy.x	Remark
Yogic Practices	1	60.058	60.058	5.689	p<0.05
Error	57	601.702	10.556		
Total	59				

From Table 1.2, it can be seen that the adjusted F-Value is 5.689 which is significant at 0.05 level with $df = 1/57$. It indicates that the adjusted mean scores of Left Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group differ significantly when their Pre-Left Leg Dynamic Balance was taken as Covariate.

Further, the adjusted mean score of Left Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group is 93.94 which is significantly higher than those of Control Group whose adjusted mean score of Left Leg Dynamic Balance is 91.93. It may, therefore, be said that Left Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players treated through Yogic Practices Group was found to be significantly superior to Control Group when groups were matched in respect of their Pre-Left Leg Dynamic Balance. The result also has been graphically presented in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: Group wise comparison of Adjusted Mean Scores of Left Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players

Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between adjusted mean scores of Left Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group by considering their Pre-Left Leg Dynamic Balance as covariate is rejected.

Groupwise comparison of adjusted mean scores of Pulse Rate:

The Objective was to compare adjusted mean scores of Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group by considering their Pre-Pulse Rate as covariate. Here Strategy of Yogic Practices was One Independent Variable having two levels, namely, Asanas and Pranayama. Pre-Pulse Rate was one Covariate and Post-Pulse Rate was the Dependent Variable. Thus, the data were analysed with the help of One Way ANCOVA and the results are given in Table 1.3.

Table 1.3: Summary of One Way ANCOVA of Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players by taking their Pre-Pulse Rate as Covariate

Source of Variance	df	SSy.x	MSSy.x	Fy.x	Remark
Yogic Practices	1	832.94	832.94	19.771	p<0.01
Error	57	2401.36	42.13		
Total	59				

From Table 1.3, it can be seen that the adjusted F-Value is 19.771 which is significant at 0.01 level with $df = 1/57$. It indicates that the adjusted mean scores of Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group differ significantly when their Pre-Pulse Rate was taken as Covariate.

Further, the adjusted mean score of Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group is 75.77 which is significantly higher than those of Control Group whose adjusted mean score of Pulse Rate is 83.33. It may, therefore, be said that Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players treated through Yogic Practices Group was found to be significantly superior to Control Group when groups were matched in respect of their Pre-Pulse Rate. The result also has been graphically presented in Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3: Group wise comparison of Adjusted Mean Scores of Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Player

Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between adjusted mean scores of Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group by considering their Pre-Pulse Rate as covariate is rejected.

Results and Discussions:

- There is no significant difference between adjusted mean scores of Right Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group by considering their Pre-Right Leg Dynamic Balance as covariate is rejected. The adjusted mean score of Right Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group is 95.53 which is significantly higher than those of Control Group whose adjusted mean score of Right Leg Dynamic Balance is 92.71.
- There is no significant difference between adjusted mean scores of Left Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group by considering their Pre-Left Leg Dynamic Balance as covariate is rejected. The adjusted mean score of Left Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group is 93.94 which is significantly higher than those of Control Group whose adjusted mean score of Left Leg Dynamic Balance is 91.93.
- There is no significant difference between adjusted mean scores of Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group and Control Group by considering their Pre-Pulse Rate as covariate is rejected. The adjusted mean score of Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players of Yogic Practices Group is 75.77 which is significantly higher than those of Control

Group whose adjusted mean score of Pulse Rate is 83.33.

Findings:

From the present experimental study it has been found that-

- The Right Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players treated through Yogic Practices Group was found to be significantly superior to Control Group when groups were matched in respect of their Pre- Right Leg Dynamic Balance.
- The Left Leg Dynamic Balance of State Level Kho Kho Players treated through Yogic Practices Group was found to be significantly superior to Control Group when groups were matched in respect of their Pre-Left Leg Dynamic Balance.
- The Pulse Rate of State Level Kho Kho Players treated through Yogic Practices Group was found to be significantly superior to Control Group when groups were matched in respect of their Pre-Pulse Rate.

Conclusion:

It was concluded that yogic practices have a positive effect on Dynamic Balance as data showing a significant improvement in Dynamic

Balance for the experimental group, with a clear reduction in reaction time after the intervention, The study of Yogic practices incorporating Omkar, Asanas, Pranayam has been significantly effective in enhancing physiological measures like Pulse Rate.

Incorporating yoga into regular training programs can enhance performance of the State level Kho Kho players.

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